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Proof of the 3D Navier-Stokes equation's global existence and smoothness of solutions – Applying a new analytical approach with certain boundary conditions

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ABSTRACT. The Navier-Stokes equations are mainly useful for describing the relationship between velocity, pressure and density of moving fluid. In the beginning of the 19th century, these partial differential equations for modeling fluid dynamics are discovered independently from each other by French and Irish physicists Claude-Louis Navier and George Gabriel Stokes. The main focus of this research paper is to discover if and under which circumstances globally defined and smooth solutions to the 3-dimensional Navier-Stokes PDEs could exist. By using an entire and exclusive analytical approach, it could be shown that under certain predefined boundary conditions and given any initial conditions, there exist solutions to the 3D Navier-Stokes equations which are indeed globally defined and smooth.

1. Introduction

In this paper, I would like to provide new evidence for the existence and smoothness of global solutions to the 3 dimensional Navier-Stokes equations which is in contrast to the common opinion of the mathematical community which states that no such globally defined and smooth solutions to these partial differential equations exist. In recent years, there are some very promising attempts to prove that globally smooth solutions for the Navier-Stokes equations exist like the one proposed by Prof. Mukhtarbay Otelbaev of the Eurasian National University in Astana, Kazakhstan¹, but these trials have turned out to be wrong in the end². Other reputed researchers like e.g. Prof. Terrence Tao have found out that the (averaged version of) the Navier-Stokes equations in 3D Space would always blow-up in finite time³.

In this piece of work, I will utilize the 3D Navier-Stokes equations provided by NASA as our first and main entry point into our research⁴ where our goal would be to find the global defined and smooth solutions of the 3-dimensional Navier-Stokes equations using a new analytical approach.

1 Prof. Otelbaev used a rather theoretical resp. abstract approach for his proof attempt there.

2 cf. Moskvitch (2014)

3 cf. Tao (2016)

4 cf. Hall (2021)

We will apply carefully chosen boundary conditions the system of partial differential equations (PDEs) which “simplifies” the PDE system and make it analytically solvable for any given initial conditions⁵.

In our first NASA model of the Navier-Stokes equations, it is important to know that because the equations are mainly used for space applications where the entities (spaceships, space stations, rockets, satellites etc.) are usually moving far away from big objects emitting gravity or electromagnetism (e.g. planets), the external forces like electromagnetism and gravity are completely insignificant and thus negligible.

Our second model is the initial NASA model using roughly the same Navier-Stokes equations like in the first model but now we just add the external forces (e.g. electromagnetism and gravity) to all the momentum equations.

2. Navier-Stokes equations in 3D for space applications without external forces

As mentioned earlier, there are many forms and possibilities to model fluid dynamics with the Navier-Stokes equations in 3-dimensional space⁶. Our starting point into our research and analysis would be the 3-dimensional Navier-Stokes equations utilized by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)⁷. The equations models relates the changes of velocity, pressure, density and temperature of moving fluids. In the beginning of the 19th century, these partial differential equations (PDEs) were derived independently by Sir George Gabriel Stokes and Claude-Louis Navier and are extensions of the Euler equations adding the effects of viscosity on the flow of fluids. In this NASA model the external forces are negligible because they are not significant because the entities moving in space are not usually not close enough to huge objects and bodies (e.g. planets, stars) emitting external gravity or electromagnetism forces⁸:

5 We only apply boundary conditions where it is absolutely necessary in order to keep the main and generic properties of the Navier-Stokes equations as untouched as possible.

6 cf. i.a. Landau and Lifshitz (1959)

7 cf. Hall (2021)

8 Even in non-space applications e.g. when we model flow of fluids on earth, it is possible that we omit the external forces from our model in certain idealized situations and experimental set up. That is why the theoretical framework provided by NASA without any external forces are still applicable to a greater extent.

Coordinates: (x, y, z) ; Velocity Components: (u, v, w)

Time: t ; Pressure: p ; Density: ρ ; Stress: τ

Reynolds Number: Re ; Prandtl Number: Pr

Total Energy: E_t ; Heat Flux: q

Continuity:

$$\frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial \rho u)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \rho v)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \rho w)}{(\partial z)} = 0$$

X - Momentum:

$$\frac{(\partial \rho u)}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial \rho u^2)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \rho uv)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \rho uw)}{(\partial z)} = - \left(\frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial x)} \right) + \frac{1}{(Re)} \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xx})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{xy})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{xz})}{(\partial z)} \right)$$

Y - Momentum:

$$\frac{(\partial \rho v)}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial \rho uv)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \rho v^2)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \rho vw)}{(\partial z)} = - \left(\frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial y)} \right) + \frac{1}{(Re)} \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xy})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yy})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yz})}{(\partial z)} \right) \quad (1)$$

Z - Momentum:

$$\frac{(\partial \rho w)}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial \rho uw)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \rho vw)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \rho w^2)}{(\partial z)} = - \left(\frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial z)} \right) + \frac{1}{(Re)} \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xz})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yz})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{zz})}{(\partial z)} \right)$$

Energy:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(\partial (E_t))}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial (u E_t))}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial (v E_t))}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial (w E_t))}{(\partial z)} = & - \left(\frac{(\partial (up))}{(\partial x)} \right) - \left(\frac{(\partial (vp))}{(\partial y)} \right) - \left(\frac{(\partial (wp))}{(\partial z)} \right) \\ & - \left(\frac{1}{(RePr)} \right) \left(\frac{(\partial q_x)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial q_y)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial q_z)}{(\partial z)} \right) \\ & + \left(\frac{1}{(Re)} \right) \left(\frac{(\partial (u \tau_{xx} + v \tau_{xy} + w \tau_{xz}))}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial (u \tau_{xy} + v \tau_{yy} + w \tau_{yz}))}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial (u \tau_{xz} + v \tau_{yz} + w \tau_{zz}))}{(\partial z)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

The equations and formulas above is the system of partial differential equations (PDEs), mainly consisting of the time-dependent continuity equation for mass conservation and the 3 momentum equations in the X, Y and Z direction explaining the conservation of energy which is time-dependent as well⁹. Our main goal in this piece of work would be to find out the effects of the 4 independent variables (which are the 3 spatial coordinates of the same domain x, y, z and time variable t) on the dependent variables pressure p and the velocity components u, v, w in different spatial directions. In order to achieve that we need to “simplify” (but not oversimplify) the above partial differential equations and apply certain boundary conditions to them so that the solutions are still as generic and meaningful as possible. As already mentioned earlier on, we will try to find the solutions analytically and not by using numerical methods.

⁹ The 5th partial differential equation relating the effects of velocity changes and changes in energy levels across 3-dimensional space and time in a world where viscous forces exist (time-dependent conservation of energy equation) is not the main focus of our analysis and it is only included for completeness reasons. It is a supportive equation and especially useful when we would like to solve the system of Navier-Stokes equations approximately using numerical methods (CFD) which is not the main focus area of this research paper.

2.1 Model with core assumptions & boundary conditions

Core assumptions (i. Space model without external forces):

1. Incompressible flow of fluids, e.g. fluid density is a constant and thus it is not dependent on (x, y, z, t):

$$\frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial t)} = \frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial z)} = 0$$

2. We only use the first 4 PDEs (continuity and 3 momentum equations), because by selecting the appropriate boundary conditions it is sufficient to find the solution of these 4 partial differential equations analytically (velocity and pressure functions).

3. Reynolds number do not need to but could be 0 (e.g. quiescent fluids like still water, lakes, deep ocean fluids are modeled as well) and that is only possible when:

$$\left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xx})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{xy})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{xz})}{(\partial z)} \right) = 0, \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xy})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yy})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yz})}{(\partial z)} \right) = 0, \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xz})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yz})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{zz})}{(\partial z)} \right) = 0$$

So that LHS = RHS hold for all the 3 momentum equations in (1) which we could see if we multiply Re on both sides of all the momentum equations (e.g. the X – Momentum equation) before we plugin Re = 0¹⁰.

4. Velocity (u,v,w) changes are assumed to be constant (symmetry) resp. the same for changes in (x, y, z, t):

$$\frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial t)} = \frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial z)} = u'$$

$$\frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial t)} = \frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial z)} = v'$$

$$\frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial t)} = \frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial z)} = w'$$

¹⁰ To make this assumption more clear: even if the Reynolds number Re would be 0 (which is an edge case and only applicable for quiescent fluids), the Navier-Stokes equations would still hold, if the sum of effects of x, y, z changes on the stress tensors are assumed to be 0. In this edge case, the LHS and RHS would be both 0 which (0 = 0) is a valid statement as well. But generally the Reynolds number Re is not assumed to be 0 in this paper. So this 3. core assumption states that the sum of effects of x, y, z changes on the stress tensors are assumed to be 0 which need to be the case especially for Re = 0 (which is an edge case) but we make this assumption also for the normal case of a positive Reynolds number (Re > 0) for simplicity and generality reasons.

5. Pressure changes are the same (another symmetry condition) for changes in (x, y, z):

$$\frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial z)} = p'$$

2.2 Main results for Navier-Stokes equations without external forces

Now when we apply the core assumptions to our 4 partial differential equations provided by NASA, firstly, the continuity equation simplifies to:

Continuity:

$$\rho \left(\frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial z)} \right) = 0, \text{ with } \frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial t)} = 0$$

because ρ is a constant (1. core assumption).

$$\rightarrow \rho(u' + v' + w') = 0,$$

due to the fact that we also assume that velocity changes are constant over changes in x, y, z, t (4. core assumption).

When dealing with the 3 momentum equations below, we at first use the product and chain rule of differentiation and then apply the 4th core assumption of constant velocity changes over spatial and time dimensions as well:

X – Momentum:

$$Re * \rho [u' + (2u(x)u') + (u'v(y) + u(y)v') + u'w(z) + u(z)w'] = -Re * p'$$

Y – Momentum:

$$Re * \rho [v' + (u'v(x) + u(x)v') + (2v(y)v') + (v'w(z) + v(z)w')] = -Re * p'$$

Z – Momentum:

$$Re * \rho [w' + (u'w(x) + u(x)w') + (v'w(y) + v(y)w') + 2w(z)w'] = -Re * p'$$

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When we substitute the derivatives (u', v', w', p') with the variables (a, b, c, d):

Continuity:

$$\rho(u' + v' + w') = 0$$

$$\rightarrow \rho(a + b + c) = 0$$

X - Momentum:

$$R e * \rho[u' + (2u(x)u') + (u'v(y) + u(y)v') + u'w(z) + u(z)w'] = -R e * p'$$

$$\rightarrow R e * \rho[a + (2u(x)a) + (av(y) + u(y)b) + aw(z) + u(z)c] = -R e * d$$

Y - Momentum:

$$R e * \rho[v' + (u'v(x) + u(x)v') + (2v(y)v') + (v'w(z) + v(z)w')] = -R e * p'$$

$$\rightarrow R e * \rho[b + (av(x) + u(x)b) + (2v(y)b) + (bw(z) + v(z)a)] = -R e * d$$

Z - Momentum:

$$R e * \rho[w' + (u'w(x) + u(x)w') + (v'w(y) + v(y)w') + 2w(z)w'] = -R e * p'$$

$$\rightarrow R e * \rho[c + (aw(x) + u(x)w') + (bw(y) + v(y)c) + 2w(z)c] = -R e * d$$

Now solving the 4 equations for the substituted variables (a, b, c, d) below:

Continuity:

$$\rho(a + b + c) = 0$$

X - Momentum:

$$R e * \rho[a + (2u(x)a) + (av(y) + u(y)b) + aw(z) + u(z)c] = -R e * d$$

Y - Momentum:

$$R e * \rho[b + (av(x) + u(x)b) + (2v(y)b) + (bw(z) + v(z)a)] = -R e * d$$

Z - Momentum:

$$R e * \rho[c + (aw(x) + u(x)c) + (bw(y) + v(y)c) + 2w(z)c] = -R e * d$$

We get the following results: (a, b, c, d) = (u', v', w', p') = (0, 0, 0, 0) thus (u, v, w, p) are the antiderivatives of (0, 0, 0, 0) = (C₁, C₂, C₃, C₄) which are 4 different constants that are globally defined and smooth.

So the changes of velocity u, v, w over x, y, z, t would always be 0, therefore (u, v, w) = (C₁, C₂, C₃) which means that as long as the velocity function are constant and are not changing over time and spatial dimensions, it does not really matter (for the solution function of the 4 PDEs to be globally defined and smooth), how fast or slow the fluid are moving across different spatial directions and time dimension. And when we consider that the changes pressure p over x, y, z would always be 0 as well, so that p = C₄, if we make sure that the pressure are constant and does not change over the spatial directions, then the solution function of the partial differential equations for pressure would be globally defined and smooth as well.

3. Navier-Stokes equations in 3-dimensional space with external forces

In the previous chapter, it is shown that globally defined and smooth solutions to the 3-dimensional Navier-Stokes equations are obtainable, if we make some additional assumptions to the model provided by NASA¹¹, like incompressible fluid flow, Reynolds number do not always need to but could be 0 as well, velocity (u,v,w) changes are assumed to be constant resp. the same for changes in (x, y, z, t) and pressure changes are the same for changes in (x, y, z) .

The results from the previous 2nd chapter were great, but since one of the main aspects of the NASA model is that it omits any external forces that act on the fluid, the NASA framework is mainly applicable for space entities or in idealized situations like experiments. In order to make the NASA model more widely adaptable for any kind of situations and applications especially on earth, I would like to add external forces (e.g. gravity & electromagnetism) to the original framework model provided by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration¹².

11 cf. Hall (2021)

12 For Navier-Stokes equations including external forces cf. i.a. Batchelor(1967) and Deak (2015)

Coordinates: (x, y, z) ; Velocity Components: (u, v, w)
 Time: t ; Pressure: p ; Density: ρ ; Stress: τ ; External force $(s): f$
 Reynolds Number: Re ; Prandtl Number: Pr
 Total Energy: E_t ; Heat Flux: q

Continuity:

$$\frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial \rho u)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \rho v)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \rho w)}{(\partial z)} = 0$$

X - Momentum:

$$\frac{(\partial \rho u)}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial \rho u^2)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \rho uv)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \rho uw)}{(\partial z)} = - \left(\frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial x)} \right) + \frac{1}{(Re)} \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xx})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{xy})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{xz})}{(\partial z)} \right) + \rho f_x$$

Y - Momentum:

$$\frac{(\partial \rho v)}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial \rho uv)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \rho v^2)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \rho vw)}{(\partial z)} = - \left(\frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial y)} \right) + \frac{1}{(Re)} \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xy})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yy})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yz})}{(\partial z)} \right) + \rho f_y \quad (2)$$

Z - Momentum:

$$\frac{(\partial \rho w)}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial \rho uw)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \rho vw)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \rho w^2)}{(\partial z)} = - \left(\frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial z)} \right) + \frac{1}{(Re)} \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xz})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yz})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{zz})}{(\partial z)} \right) + \rho f_z$$

Energy:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(\partial (E_t))}{(\partial t)} + \frac{(\partial (u E_t))}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial (v E_t))}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial (w E_t))}{(\partial z)} = & - \left(\frac{(\partial (up))}{(\partial x)} \right) - \left(\frac{(\partial (vp))}{(\partial y)} \right) - \left(\frac{(\partial (wp))}{(\partial z)} \right) \\ & - \left(\frac{1}{(RePr)} \right) \left(\frac{(\partial q_x)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial q_y)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial q_z)}{(\partial z)} \right) \\ & + \left(\frac{1}{(Re)} \right) \left(\frac{(\partial (u \tau_{xx} + v \tau_{xy} + w \tau_{xz}))}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial (u \tau_{xy} + v \tau_{yy} + w \tau_{yz}))}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial (u \tau_{xz} + v \tau_{yz} + w \tau_{zz}))}{(\partial z)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

As we can see above, the external forces ρf_i (e.g. gravity, electromagnetism) are added to the right-hand side of all the 3 momentum equations. Other than this adjustment, all the other properties of the Navier-Stokes equations are exactly the same like in the original NASA model framework. And just like in the initial model of NASA, our main goal is to find the effects of the 4 independent variables (which are the 3 spatial coordinates of the same domain x, y, z and time variable t) on the dependent variables pressure p and the velocity components u, v, w in different spatial directions¹³. Just like in the 2nd Chapter, we are going to find the solutions analytically, after we have applied some important boundary conditions to the PDEs to make these equations analytically solvable so that the solutions are still as generic and meaningful as possible.

13 Just like in the previous Chapter 2, the 5th partial differential equation relating the effects of velocity changes and changes in energy levels across 3D space and time in a world where viscous forces exist (time-dependent conservation of energy equation) is not the main focus of our analysis and it is only included for completeness reasons. It is a supportive equation and especially useful when we would like to solve the system of Navier-Stokes equations approximately using numerical methods (CFD) which is not the main focus area in this piece of work.

3.1 Model with core assumptions & boundary conditions

Core assumptions (ii. Model including external forces):

1. Incompressible flow of fluids, e.g. fluid density is a constant and therefore not dependent on (x, y, z, t):

$$\frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial t)} = \frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial z)} = 0$$

2. We only use the first 4 PDEs (continuity and 3 momentum equations) because by choosing the appropriate boundary conditions it is sufficient to find the solution of these 4 partial differential equations analytically (velocity and pressure functions).

3. Reynolds number do not always have to but could be 0 (e.g. quiescent fluids like still water, lakes, deep ocean fluids are modelled as well) and that is only possible when the sum of total effects on the stress tensors for changes in the spatial coordinates are all canceled out to be zero:

$$\left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xx})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{xy})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{xz})}{(\partial z)} \right) = 0, \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xy})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yy})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yz})}{(\partial z)} \right) = 0, \left(\frac{(\partial \tau_{xz})}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{yz})}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial \tau_{zz})}{(\partial z)} \right) = 0$$

So that LHS = RHS hold for all the 3 momentum equations in (1) which we could see if we multiply Re on both sides of all the momentum equations (e.g. the X – Momentum equation) before we plugin Re = 0¹⁴.

4. Velocity (u,v,w) changes are assumed to be constant (symmetry) resp. the same for changes in (x, y, z, t):

$$\frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial t)} = \frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial z)} = u'$$

$$\frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial t)} = \frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial z)} = v'$$

$$\frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial t)} = \frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial z)} = w'$$

14 To make this assumption more clear once again: even if the Reynolds number Re would be 0 (which is an edge case and only applicable for quiescent fluids), the Navier-Stokes equations would still hold, if the sum of effects of x, y, z changes on the stress tensors are assumed to be 0. In this edge case, the LHS and RHS would be both 0 which (0 = 0) is a valid statement as well. But generally the Reynolds number Re is not assumed to be 0 in this paper. So this 3. core assumption states that the sum of effects of x, y, z changes on the stress tensors are assumed to be 0 which need to be the case especially for Re = 0 (which is an edge case) but we make this assumption also for the normal case of a positive Reynolds number (Re > 0) for simplicity and generality reasons.

5. Pressure changes are the same (another symmetry condition) for changes in (x, y, z):

$$\frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial x)} = \frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial y)} = \frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial z)} = p'$$

6. External forces f exist and are acting with the same strength (another symmetry condition) to the fluid in all spatial dimensions (x, y, z):

$$f_x = f_y = f_z = f \neq 0$$

So the 6th and last boundary condition is newly added to the other boundary conditions which are the same like in the original NASA model (without external forces) presented in the previous chapter before.

3.2 Main results for Navier-Stokes equations including external forces

When we apply the main assumptions to the 4 PDEs including external forces for the momentum equations, first of all, the continuity equation simplifies to:

$$\text{Continuity: } \rho \left(\frac{(\partial u)}{(\partial x)} + \frac{(\partial v)}{(\partial y)} + \frac{(\partial w)}{(\partial z)} \right) = 0, \text{ with } \frac{(\partial \rho)}{(\partial t)} = 0$$

because ρ is a constant (1. core assumption).

$$\rightarrow \rho(u' + v' + w') = 0,$$

since we also assume that velocity changes are constant over changes in x, y, z, t (4. core assumption).

When dealing with the 3 momentum equations below, we firstly apply the product and chain rule of differentiation and then use the 4th core assumption of constant velocity changes over spatial and time dimensions as well:

X - Momentum:

$$\begin{aligned} R e * \rho [u' + (2u(x)u') + (u'v(y) + u(y)v') + u'w(z) + u(z)w'] &= -R e * p' + R e * \rho * f_x \\ \rightarrow R e * \rho [u' + (2u(x)u') + (u'v(y) + u(y)v') + u'w(z) + u(z)w'] &= -R e * p' + R e * \rho * f \end{aligned}$$

That is because $f_x = f_y = f_z = f \neq 0$ (6. core assumption of model ii.).

Y - Momentum:

$$\begin{aligned} R e * \rho [v' + (u'v(x) + u(x)v') + (2v(y)v') + (v'w(z) + v(z)w')] &= -R e * p' + R e * \rho * f_y \\ \rightarrow R e * \rho [v' + (u'v(x) + u(x)v') + (2v(y)v') + (v'w(z) + v(z)w')] &= -R e * p' + R e * \rho * f \end{aligned}$$

That is because $f_x = f_y = f_z = f \neq 0$ (6. core assumption of model ii.).

Z - Momentum:

$$\begin{aligned} R e * \rho [w' + (u'w(x) + u(x)w') + (v'w(y) + v(y)w') + 2w(z)w'] &= -R e * p' + R e * \rho * f_z \\ \rightarrow R e * \rho [w' + (u'w(x) + u(x)w') + (v'w(y) + v(y)w') + 2w(z)w'] &= -R e * p' + R e * \rho * f \end{aligned}$$

That is because $f_x = f_y = f_z = f \neq 0$ (6. core assumption of model ii.).

When we substitute the derivatives (u', v', w', p') with the variables (a, b, c, d):

Continuity:

$$\rho(u' + v' + w') = 0$$

$$\rightarrow \rho(a + b + c) = 0$$

X - Momentum:

$$\begin{aligned} R e * \rho [u' + (2u(x)u') + (u'v(y) + u(y)v') + u'w(z) + u(z)w'] &= -R e * p' + R e * \rho * f \\ \rightarrow R e * \rho [a + (2u(x)a) + (av(y) + u(y)b) + aw(z) + u(z)c] &= R e(\rho * f - d) \end{aligned}$$

Y - Momentum:

$$\begin{aligned} R e * \rho [v' + (u'v(x) + u(x)v') + (2v(y)v') + (v'w(z) + v(z)w')] &= -R e * p' + R e * \rho * f \\ \rightarrow R e * \rho [b + (av(x) + u(x)b) + (2v(y)b) + (bw(z) + v(z)a)] &= R e(\rho * f - d) \end{aligned}$$

Z - Momentum:

$$\begin{aligned} R e * \rho [w' + (u'w(x) + u(x)w') + (v'w(y) + v(y)w') + 2w(z)w'] &= -R e * p' + R e * \rho * f \\ \rightarrow R e * \rho [c + (aw(x) + u(x)c) + (bw(y) + v(y)c) + 2w(z)c] &= R e(\rho * f - d) \end{aligned}$$

Now solving the 4 partial differential equations for the substituted variables (a, b, c, d) below:

Continuity:

$$\rho(a+b+c)=0$$

X – Momentum:

$$R e * \rho [a+(2u(x)a)+(av(y)+u(y)b)+aw(z)+u(z)c] = R e (\rho * f - d)$$

Y – Momentum:

$$R e * \rho [b+(av(x)+u(x)b)+(2v(y)b)+(bw(z)+v(z)a)] = R e (\rho * f - d)$$

Z – Momentum:

$$R e * \rho [c+(aw(x)+u(x)w')+(bw(y)+v(y)c)+2w(z)c] = R e (\rho * f - d)$$

We get the following results: (a, b, c, d) = (u', v', w', p') = (0, 0, 0, ρf) thus the velocity variables (u, v, w) are the antiderivatives of (0, 0, 0) = (C₁, C₂, C₃) which results in 3 different constants that are globally defined and smooth.

As for the pressure variable(s):

$$d = p' = \rho f$$

$$\rightarrow p' = \frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial x)} = \rho f \Leftrightarrow p(x) = \int (\rho f) dx = \rho f * x + K_1$$

$$\rightarrow p' = \frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial y)} = \rho f \Leftrightarrow p(y) = \int (\rho f) dy = \rho f * y + K_2$$

$$\rightarrow p' = \frac{(\partial p)}{(\partial z)} = \rho f \Leftrightarrow p(z) = \int (\rho f) dz = \rho f * z + K_3$$

Therefore the pressure variable(s) are globally defined and smooth as well for finite (x, y, z) and for any initial conditions with finite pressure levels (K₁, K₂, K₃) under the given and applied core assumptions¹⁵ in the NASA model adding external gravitational and electromagnetic forces.

15 Let us recall that one of the most important of the core assumptions are that the external forces f_i are the same across different spatial dimensions (x, y, z). If this were not the case, then the solution functions of the 4 PDEs gets rather complicated and chaotic: complicated fractions would exist in all of the solutions functions for the pressure p and the velocity components (u, v, w). And because we can not rule out that the denominator of the fractional solution functions to the PDEs will never be zero, we can not be sure that the solution functions would not blow up for finite time t or spatial components (x, y, z).

4. Conclusions

It should be stated here once again, that this research paper serves the purpose in finding globally defined and smooth solutions to 3-dimensional Navier-Stokes equations. In the past there have been various attempts to find and analyze the solutions of these partial differential equations, either reaching the conclusion that the solutions of the 3D Navier-Stokes equations would always blow up in finite time¹⁶ or that the proposed proof of global existence and smoothness of the solutions to the Navier-Stokes PDEs are in fact incorrect¹⁷.

Because most of the methods in trying to obtain the solutions to the 3-dimensional Navier-Stokes equations are using numerical methods (or a combined numerical and analytical approach) or using completely abstract methods without directly trying to find the solutions, in this piece of work, the main focus was and is to use a concrete and completely analytical approach in obtaining the solutions to the Navier-Stokes partial differential equations in 3D. There are 2 main models used in this paper:

1. Navier-Stokes equations in 3D without external forces¹⁸
2. Navier-Stokes equations in 3D including external forces which are added to the first model above¹⁹

Because in both model frameworks there are far more variables than (partial differential) equations, we try to “simplify” the original equations by applying our boundary conditions like incompressible flow of fluids, Reynolds number do not always have to but could be 0, velocity (u,v,w) changes are assumed to be constant (symmetry condition) resp. the same for changes in (x, y, z, t), pressure changes are the same (another symmetry condition) for changes in (x, y, z) and external forces f exist and are acting with the same strength (further symmetry condition) to the fluid in all spatial dimensions (x, y, z) with the 6th and last boundary condition which is only applied in the 2nd model with the Navier-Stokes equations modeling external forces like e.g. gravity and electromagnetism acting on the fluid.

16 cf. Tao (2016) for his combined numerical and analytical approach in tackling the (average) version of the Navier-Stokes equations in 3D.

17 cf. Moskvitch (2014) which elaborates on Prof. Otelbaev’s unsuccessful attempt to prove the global existence and smoothness of solutions to 3-dimensional Navier-Stokes equations using a rather theoretical and abstract approach.

18 cf. Hall (2021) for the original Navier-Stokes equations of NASA

19 cf. i.a. Batchelor (1967) and Deak (2015) for Navier-Stokes equations with external forces

The analytical solutions to the first model yields 4 different constants for the velocity and pressure components which tells us that the exact velocity or pressure levels are not really important for finding globally defined and smooth solutions to the partial differential equations, the most important aspect is that those velocities and pressure levels do not change in order for the PDEs yielding smooth and globally defined solution functions.

The solutions to the 2nd model with external forces (which are assumed to equal to each other across different spatial dimensions²⁰) are 3 different constants for the velocity components in 3 different spatial directions and for the pressure function, it is a linear function with each one dependent on different spatial coordinates (x, y, z) and valid for any initial condition for the initial pressure levels as long as the initial pressure levels are finite across all spatial dimensions. Under these circumstances of velocity levels not changing and pressure to be linear functions, the solutions to the 3D Navier-Stokes equations are globally defined and smooth as well given that all the predefined boundary conditions do apply.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors whose names are listed immediately below certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers’ bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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²⁰ In practical scenarios within or beyond experiments, in order to achieve equality for external forces across different spatial dimensions, we could try to balance out the given gravitational forces with e. g. electromagnetism.

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